

Fuel-Saving Potential of Different Bulk Carriers using Air Lubrication Systems

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Abstract. Due to the impact of global warming, there is an increasing motivation to improve the energy efficiency of propulsion systems or use new technologies to reduce ship energy consumption. Air lubrication systems (ALS) have been proposed as a promising energy-saving technology that can effectively reduce fuel consumption and greenhouse gas emissions of ships. However, the current evaluation indicators for ALS to reduce ship energy consumption mainly use power saving rate or drag reduction rate, which cannot intuitively reflect the fuel saving effect of the entire ship. At the same time, the fuel saving effect of ALS on different ship types may also be different. This paper employs the Holtrop method to estimate ship resistance and extends the drag reduction rate obtained from experimental calculations to full-scale with the application of an air lubrication system. The main engine output power is determined based on the force equilibrium principle in steady sailing, while also considering variations in diesel generator load from the air lubrication system. A regression analysis is conducted to establish the relationship between fuel consumption and the load on both the main engine and diesel generators. Furthermore, a gray-box ship fuel consumption model incorporating air lubrication technology is developed using MATLAB/Simulink for simulation. By applying air lubrication technology to six different types of bulk carrier - Small, Handysize, Handymax, Panamax, Capesize and VLBC - the fuel saving effects of different ship types when using ALS are compared. The results show that VLBC bulk carriers achieve the highest fuel savings at higher speeds, while smaller ship types exhibit more significant drag reduction effects. Notably, small bulk carriers can achieve a fuel saving rate of up to 16.3% at a speed of 14 knots.

Keywords: Air Lubrication System, Modelling, Simulation, Bulk carriers.

1 Introduction

Due to the impacts of global warming and air pollution, various regulations and standards to limit the emission of greenhouse gases and air-quality pollutants have been formulated and implemented [1]. As restrictions on carbon emissions from ships become increasingly stringent, the shipping industry is actively adopting new technologies to comply with the regulatory requirements [2]. The air lubrication system (ALS) is an energy saving device that reduces the frictional resistance of the hull by forming a layer of microbubbles at the bottom of the hull, thereby reducing the power demand of the main engine (ME) and fuel consumption [3].

ALS demonstrates multiple comparative advantages over other energy saving devices. First, its operational performance is only minimally affected by environmental conditions, which gives it broader applicability compared to climate-dependent technologies such as wind-assisted propulsion. Second, the system requires the installation of air injection devices only along the bottom of the hull. This arrangement does not interfere with deck operations or reduce cargo hold capacity, thus minimising negative impacts on the vessel's operational efficiency. Third, the overall system weight is relatively low. In contrast to large-scale energy-saving equipment such as sails or waste heat recovery systems, ALS imposes limited additional weight on the vessel. This helps avoid increased fuel consumption that may result from higher deadweight. In addition to reducing greenhouse gas emissions, hull air lubrication can also help mitigate underwater noise by minimizing vibrations, engine noise, and the accumulation of marine organisms [4]. Due to these technical advantages, ALS has attracted more and more attention from the shipping industry and researchers.

Kodama et al. conducted experiments using model ships, confirming that bubbles reduced both the total resistance acting on the model and the local friction acting on the ship's bottom [5]. Park et al. conducted an experiment on an oil tanker model, achieving a drag reduction of 18.1% by selecting the optimal air injection

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configuration and the distribution ratio between two injectors [6]. Kim et al. built an ALS energy-saving model, which showed a potential net power savings rate of 3-24% for the global fleet [7].

Although research on air lubrication system has been relatively extensive, current studies primarily use indicators for the potential for an ALS to reduce ship energy consumption mainly use power saving rate or drag reduction rate. However, these metrics do not intuitively reflect the fuel saving effect of the whole ship. At the same time, the fuel saving effect of an ALS may also vary for different ship types. Therefore, to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the application prospects of ALS, this study compares and analyses the fuel saving effect of various types of bulk carrier. This will allow shipping companies to better evaluate the application value of air lubrication systems for different bulk carriers, thereby effectively reducing fuel consumption and improving the economic benefits of overall operations.

The rest of this paper is organised as follows: The materials and modelling method will be introduced in Section 2. The simulation results of fuel saving using air lubrication systems on different ships are analysed in Section 3. Section 4 presents the conclusions, summarising the fuel saving potential of using ALS on six different bulk carriers.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Ship Specifications

Six different types of bulk carrier are used as reference ships in this study - Small, Handysize, Handymax, Panamax, Capesize and VLBC. The dimensions, size and ME Maximum Continuous Rating (MCR) Power parameters of the reference ships are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Main parameters of the target ship

Classes	Dimensions (L×B×D, m)	Size (DWT)	ME MCR Power (kW)
Small	115×15.26 ×11.5	14500	1×5500
Handysize	170×26.3 ×10	33500	1×8250
Handymax	190×32.26 ×11.5	53000	1×10500
Panamax	225×32.3 ×13.1	71000	1×11500
Capesize	285×45 ×18	172000	1×18000
VLBC	300×50 ×18.73	205000	1×20900

The electrical power requirements of different types of bulk carrier using air lubrication systems, P_g , can be calculated using Eq. (1).

$$P_g = P_S + P_{A,L} \quad (1)$$

where $P_{A,L}$ is the electrical power requirement of the air jet pump when using air lubrication technology and P_S is the power requirement of the bulk carrier when sailing at sea, as shown in Table 2 [8].

Table 2. Bulk carrier power requirements

Type	Vessel		Power demand (kW)		
	Size (dwt)	Berth	Anchor	Man.	Sea
Bulk carrier	0-9999	110	180	500	190
	10000-34999	110	180	500	190
	35000-59999	150	250	680	260
	60000-99999	240	400	1100	410
	100000-199999	240	400	1100	410
	200000-+	240	400	1100	410

2.2 Ship Resistance

In this paper, the resistance mainly considers the hydrostatic resistance. The hydrostatic resistance refers to the resistance generated by the water on the hull when the ship is sailing in calm water. According to the Holtrop resistance estimation method, the ship's calm water resistance can be expressed as Eq. (2) [9].

$$R_t = R_f(1 + k_1) + R_{app} + R_w + R_b + R_{tr} + R_a \quad (2)$$

where R_t is the total hydrostatic resistance, R_f is the frictional resistance, k_1 the viscous resistance factor from different ship types, R_{app} is the appendage resistance, R_w is the wave-making resistance, R_b is the bulbous bow resistance, R_{tr} is the transom resistance and R_a is the model correlation resistance.

(1) Frictional resistance

Frictional resistance is the resistance due to the friction of the water flow against the surface of the hull. This part of resistance usually accounts for a larger proportion of the total resistance. The frictional resistance can be expressed as Eq. (3) [9].

$$R_f = \frac{1}{2} C_f \rho S V_s^2 \quad (3)$$

where C_f is the coefficient of frictional resistance, ρ is the density of seawater, S is the wetted area, and V_s is the ship speed through water.

According to the calculation guidelines recommended by ITTC in 1957 [9], C_f can be calculated by the Eq. (4).

$$C_f = \frac{0.075}{(\log_{10} R_e - 2)^2} \quad (4)$$

where R_e is the Reynolds number, which can be obtained by Eq. (5).

$$R_e = \frac{V_s L_{wl}}{\nu} \quad (5)$$

where ν is the dynamic viscosity of water and L_{wl} is waterline length.

(2) Appendage resistance

Appendage resistance refers to the resistance or drag caused by the presence of the parts or appendages of a ship that extend into the water, such as the bilge keels, rudder, propeller, or any other protruding parts. The formula used here for calculating the appendage resistance is given by Eq. (6) [9].

$$R_{app} = 0.5 \rho V_s^2 S_{app} (1 + k_2)_{eq} C_f \quad (6)$$

where S_{app} is wetted surface area of a ship's appendages, $1+k_2$ is the shape factor of ship appendages.

(3) Wave-making resistance

Wave-making resistance is the resistance produced by waves generated when a ship moves in water. It is the most important component of resistance at higher speeds, and wave resistance is proportional to the square of the ship's speed and the amount of water displaced by the hull. The formula used here for calculating R_w is [9]:

$$R_w = C_1 C_2 C_5 \Delta \rho e^{\{m_1 Fr^{-0.9} + m_2 \cos(\lambda Fr^{-2})\}} \quad (7)$$

where Δ is the displacement volume of a ship, in m^3 , C_1 , C_2 , C_5 , m_1 , m_2 and λ are all coefficients, which are determined by relevant calculation formulas.

The formula for the Froude number Fr is as shown in Eq. (8)

$$Fr = \frac{V_s}{\sqrt{gL_{wl}}} \quad (8)$$

where g is the gravitational acceleration, taken as 9.8 m/s^2 .

(4) Bulbus bow resistance

Bulbus bow resistance is a term used in ship hydrodynamics to describe the additional resistance or drag created by the bulbous bow on the front of a ship. The bulbous bow is a protrusion or bulb-like shape that extends from the hull of the ship below the waterline. It can be calculated by the following Eq. (9) [9].

$$R_b = \frac{0.11e^{(-3P_h^{-2})} Fr_i^3 A_{BT}^{1.5} \rho g}{(1 + Fr_i^2)} \quad (9)$$

where P_h is related to the water immersion depth of the bow, Fr_i is the Froude number based on the water immersion, A_{BT} is the transverse sectional area of the ship.

Since the bulbous bow resistance accounts for a small amount of the total hydrostatic resistance, usually less than one ten-thousandth, the bulbous bow resistance is not considered in the modelling in this paper.

(5) Transom resistance

Ship transom resistance refers to the resistance or drag created by the flat or slightly curved stern of a ship, which is known as the transom. R_{tr} can be calculated by the following Eq. (10) [9].

$$R_{tr} = 0.5\rho V_s^2 A_T C_6 \quad (10)$$

where A_T is the midship sectional area of the immersed stern, $A_T=0.051A_M=0.051BdC_M$, C_M is the midship section coefficient, C_6 is related to the Froude number of the immersed stern, when $F_{rd}<5$, $C_6=0.2(1-0.2F_{rd})$, when $F_{rd}\geq 5$, $C_6=0$. F_{rd} is the Froude number of immersion.

(6) model correlation resistance

Ship model correlation resistance refers to the process of comparing the measured resistance of a ship model in a towing tank to the predicted resistance of a full-scale ship. The aim of this process is to validate the accuracy of the ship model and the reliability of the methods used to predict the performance of the full-scale ship. The formula for R_a is [9]:

$$R_a = 0.5\rho V_s^2 S C_A \quad (11)$$

where C_A is the correlation allowance coefficient.

2.3 Air lubrication System

An ALS uses gas injectors installed at the bottom of the ship to release compressed air, forming a layer of micro-bubbles as a blanket under the hull, thereby lowering frictional resistance. Its main principle is to reduce frictional resistance by reducing direct contact area with the water, that is, by releasing bubbles and covering part of the bottom surface of the hull to reduce the wetted surface area. Due to the complexity of bubble flow, this paper calculates the drag reduction rate by combining the drag reduction effects under different air flow rates (Fig. 1) by Zhao et al. [10]. Based on three different drag reduction zones—microbubble drag reduction, air lubrication layer, and the zone between them—the drag reduction rates are interpolated for different Froude numbers and air injection rates. This approach integrates theory with data to model the air injection drag reduction technology using a gray-box model.

Figure 1. The drag reduction efficiency in the experiments at different air flow rates (adapted from [10])

As can be seen from Fig. 1, to better ensure the fluid dynamics similarity between the experiment and the full-scale ship, and to make the analysis of drag reduction efficiency at different air flow rates more scientific and scalable, different Froude numbers are given in the figure to analyse the drag reduction efficiency under different air flow rates. When the Froude number is the same, the full-scale ship speed can be calculated from the model ship speed using Eq. (8).

The drag reduction rate η_R using ALS is defined as Eq (12).

$$\eta_R = \frac{R_0 - R}{R_0} \times 100\% \quad (12)$$

The required power for air injection is estimated as the power required to compress a given amount of air through a multidirectional process at standard atmospheric pressure [3].

$$P_{\text{con}} = \frac{m_{\text{Air}}}{\eta_c \rho_{g,a}} \cdot p_1 \cdot \frac{n}{(n-1)} \left(\left[\frac{p_2}{p_1} \right]^{(n-1)/n} - 1 \right) \quad (13)$$

where m_{Air} is the mass flow rate of the injected air, the multiple index n is replaced by the air specific heat ratio $k=1.40$, $\rho_{g,a}$ is the initial density of the compressed air, η_c is the compressor efficiency, p_1 is the initial pressure, assumed to be 1atm, p_2 is the pressure the gas needs to be compressed to, which can be calculated by using Eq. (14) [3].

$$p_2 = p_1 + \rho_s \cdot g \cdot T + \Delta p \quad (14)$$

where ρ_s is the density of seawater.

Since the air injection rate in Fig. 1 is based on an experimental ship model, it needs to be converted into the air injection rate of the actual size ship, which can be obtained through Eqs. (15) and (16) [3].

$$t_{\text{AL}} = \frac{Q_{\text{Air}}}{V_{\text{Inflow}} \cdot B_{\text{Air}}} \quad (15)$$

$$t_{\text{AL}} = \frac{Q_{\text{Air}}}{V_s \cdot B_{\text{Unit}}} \quad (16)$$

where Q_{Air} is the volume flow rate of injected air, and B_{Unit} is the width of the injected air unit.

2.4 Ship fuel Consumption

For ships equipped with ALS, a layer of microbubbles is formed under the hull to reduce the resistance encountered during sailing, thereby reducing the propulsion power required from the main engine. When the ship is sailing at a steady speed, the propeller thrust balances the hull resistance, and this relationship can be described by Eqs. (17) and (18).

$$R_A = R_t \cdot (100\% - \eta_R) = T_E \quad (17)$$

$$P_E = T_E \cdot V_S = R \cdot (100\% - \eta_R) \cdot V_S \quad (18)$$

where R_A is the total resistance using ALS, T_E is the effective thrust of the propeller and P_E is the effective power of propeller.

Due to losses associated with the propeller, the power delivered to the propeller P_D must be greater than the effective power of propeller P_E . The ratio of the effective power to the delivered power is called the quasi propulsive coefficient η_D , which is usually between 0.55 and 0.65 [11]. Therefore, the power transfer relationships are illustrated by Eqs. (19) and (20).

$$P_D = P_E / \eta_D \quad (19)$$

$$P_B = P_D / (\eta_G \cdot \eta_S) \quad (20)$$

where P_B is the main engine power output, η_G is the gearbox efficiency, η_S is the shaft transmission efficiency.

According to the research by Deng et al., the propulsion efficiency loss using the air lubrication system is less than 1%, indicating that the impact of bubbles on the propeller may be minimal [12]. Based on this finding, and in the interest of model simplicity, this study neglects the variation in propulsion efficiency caused by bubbles.

The fuel oil consumption of the main engine can be determined using Specific Fuel Oil Consumption (SFOC) of the main engine and Eqs. (21) and (22).

$$q_m = P_B \cdot g_m \quad (21)$$

$$FC_m = q_m \times t \quad (22)$$

where q_m is the hourly fuel consumption of the ship, g_m is the SFOC of the main engine, FC_m is the total fuel consumption of the ME, t is the runtime of the engine (in hours).

The fuel consumption of the diesel generator (D/G) can be determined using the quadratic regression polynomial of the fuel consumption of the diesel generator set at different loads and Eq. (23).

$$FC_g = \sum_{i=1}^n q_{g,i}(P_g) \times t_i \quad (14)$$

where FC_g is the total fuel consumption of the D/Gs, q_g is the consumption rate (kg/h), i is the number of D/Gs in operation.

Overall, the total energy consumption of the ship is given by the sum of the ME fuel consumption and the fuel consumption of the D/Gs, as shown in Eq. (24).

$$FC = FC_m + FC_g \quad (14)$$

where FC is the total fuel consumption of the ship.

2.5 Power distribution strategy

The electrical distribution system model using the ALS is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. Power distribution system model using ALS

It can be seen from the figure that three D/Gs are used to power the ALS and other electrical loads on the ship. Due to the small difference in fuel consumption of D/Gs with different installed powers when using air lubrication technology, it is assumed that all six types of bulk carriers are equipped with three 500kW D/Gs, and the D/G fuel consumption using ALS is calculated. In the study by Yiğit et al. [13], quadratic regression polynomials were used for fuel consumption under different loads of 500 kW D/Gs. Their findings showed that operating the generator at 90% capacity, instead of 40%, results in lower fuel consumption and reduced fuel costs. Based on this, the load-sharing limit for the generator is set to 90% [13]. The load sharing practice between three different generators can be seen in Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Load sharing practice between generators

3 Results and discussion

A ship fuel consumption model for the ship equipped with ALS was developed, and the electrical load after adopting ALS was allocated according to the developed diesel generator power allocation strategy.

To compare the impact of different speeds on the fuel efficiency of the ship equipped with ALS, the fuel consumption and fuel savings rates for different types of bulk carriers were calculated at different ship speeds with an air injection rate of 10 m³/h, as shown in Fig. 4 and Table 3.

Figure 4. Comparison of fuel consumption and fuel saving for different ship types and different speeds

Table 3. Main parameters of the target ship

Classes	Fuel saving amount (kg/h)	Fuel saving rate (%)
Small	128.1	15.9
Handysize	144.2	13.8
Handymax	181.9	13.3
Panamax	190.7	12.3
Capesize	309.0	10.6
VLBC	335.5	10.1

As can be seen from Fig. 4, as the speed increases, the fuel saving efficiency of the six types of bulk carriers rises. This is because as the ship speed increases, the bubbles formed by the air injection are more easily evenly distributed on the bottom of the ship, forming a stable and continuous bubble layer. This not only effectively reduces the frictional resistance between the hull and the water but also significantly enhances the drag reduction performance of the air lubrication system, leading to greater fuel savings. At a maximum design speed of 14 knots, the fuel saving rate varies from 10.1% for the VLBC to 15.9% for the Small sized bulk carrier when using ALS. The VLBC has the highest hourly fuel consumption so, although it has the lowest fuel saving rate at the selected speed, it still saves the most fuel.

To compare the impact of different air injection rates on the fuel efficiency of the ship equipped with ALS, the fuel consumption and fuel savings rates for different types of bulk carriers were calculated at different air injection rates with a ship speed of 14 kn, as shown in Fig. 5.

As can be seen from Fig. 5, varying the air injection rate from 6 to 10 m³/h has little effect on the fuel consumption of each ship type, as this range falls within the air lubrication layer zone. At this stage, a continuous and stable bubble layer has already formed beneath the hull, effectively minimising hull–water contact. Further increases in air injection do not significantly reduce the contact area, resulting in a saturated drag reduction effect and a fuel saving rate that no longer improves appreciably. Additionally, Handysize, Handymax, Panamax, Capesize, and VLBC bulk carriers have the best fuel saving effect when the air injection rate is 10 m³/h. Continuing to increase the air injection rate has limited impact on fuel saving but will increase the D/G load and fuel consumption, resulting in an increase in total fuel consumption. However, the Small bulk carrier reached its optimal drag reduction rate with an air injection rate of 6 m³/h.

Figure 5. Comparison of fuel consumption and fuel saving for different ship types and different air injection rate

4 Conclusion

The fuel consumption models of six different types of bulk carrier, including small, Handysize, Handymax, Panamax, Capesize carriers and VLBC, when using ALS were developed. The simulation results show that a higher speed may achieve a more significant drag reduction effect. The highest fuel saving rate is for small bulk carriers at 14 kn, with a fuel saving rate of up to 16.3%. The maximum fuel saving capacity is for the VLBC at 14 kn, which is 335.5kg/h. In the air layer drag reduction area of the ship, when the drag reduction rate increases to a certain extent, continuing to increase the air injection rate has little positive effect on fuel saving, and may lead to an increase in total fuel consumption due to the increase in D/G fuel consumption.

The future research should focus on optimising the air injection rate for different ship types and operating conditions to achieve a balance between drag reduction and total fuel consumption. Additionally, it is also recommended to explore the long-term operational performance and economic feasibility of ALS under varied sea states and voyage profiles.

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